

THE PROBLEM OF EFFECTIVE USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation: In the article, the issue of organizing educational and educational activities based on pedagogical technologies in preschool educational organizations was studied and analyzed.

Key words: organization of preschool education, modern pedagogical technologies, methodological developments, principles of education.

INTRODUCTION

The head of our state, Sh. Mirziyoyev, in his work "Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility - should be the daily rule of every leader's activity", education and science, implementation of the state's youth policy, They critically analyzed the state of affairs in the field of introducing new, modern methods of education, including information and communication technologies, and paid attention to the implementation of a number of tasks. One of them is the fundamental reform of the educational process.

In recent years, in the education system of the new generation, we have gathered the advanced achievements of world science and culture, based on our national and spiritual values, which were created as a product of the intelligence of our ancestors, to form modern methods of education. a problem has arisen. A perfect generation is the basis of society's development. Therefore, in our country, providing education to the mentally and physically mature generation has been raised to the level of state policy. Law "On Education", "National Institute of Personnel Training", Law "On the Basics of State Policy Regarding Youth in the

Republic of Uzbekistan", and "State National Program for the Development of School Education" , "2008-2012 State program to modernize the content of the continuous education system and raise the efficiency of education to a new level of quality", in the "Strategy of Actions" for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the development strategy until 2030 and other regulatory documents set the tasks of reforming the continuous education system, which is the basis for successful implementation of working with students in the educational process, forming them as a mature generation at the state level.

After all, the opinion of the President of our country, Sh. Mirziyoyev, that "we consider improving the activity of all links of the education and training system based on the requirements of today's times as our first priority task" is of great importance. Educational practice shows that the establishment of interdisciplinarity in school education is a vivid expression of the integration processes taking place in the life of science and society today. This connection plays an important role in students' conscious assimilation of knowledge, development of a holistic vision of the world, and improvement of their practical and scientific-methodical preparation. Such training gives general secondary education graduates the opportunity to freely apply the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in class and extracurricular activities, in production and in general in any activity. Scientific achievements and their impact on people's lives developed countries will not fail to influence the content and structure of school education. As a result of the reforms being carried out in the field of education in our country, teaching hours have been drastically reduced, and the content of educational materials has been modernized. As a result of the reduction of hours in teaching various educational subjects, the scientific complexity of the content of educational materials, the demands placed on students have increased, and some declines in education are observed. Such declines in students' mastery of educational materials will not fail to affect the intellectual development of the

younger generation. This situation requires teachers to study different phenomena based on connections within the same subject. Studying natural phenomena, their structure, essence and functions, laws helps to develop thinking operations such as comparison, analysis and synthesis, abstraction, generalization, inductive and deductive conclusion in students' thinking.

In the national model of personnel training, the development of new fundamental and practical directions of science about nature and society, the training of highly qualified pedagogical personnel with scientific potential, and the improvement of their scientific literacy and skills at the level of integration of world science are the general objectives on this basis. updating the content of education and training in secondary schools, raising the quality and efficiency, improving theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications of students in each subject. Educating a free-thinking, creative, well-rounded individual who is loyal to the ideology of independence of our country requires increasing the effectiveness of primary education. From this point of view, the creation of the rules of interdisciplinary communication, the composition of the system of communication provides a solution to promising tasks in education. Even if the development of the theory of interdisciplinarity is differentiated, in practice, integration and interrelationship will further increase the social importance of science. In recent years, scientific research dedicated to solving the problems of interdisciplinarity is a requirement of social life

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

It is known that any technology is based on educational principles that form a new content of education, and it includes innovative ideas in preschool education, education of the learner's personality, work and educational skills in certain directions. directed to produce. The active subjects of the educational process are the teacher and the students, and their collaborative activities provide an opportunity for in-depth assimilation of theoretical and practical knowledge on

a specific topic (or the basics of subjects) with little effort and time spent. Pedagogical technologies aimed at activating and speeding up the educational process, in contrast to the methodical development of the educational process, for educators to be active and effective in organizing educational and educational activities in preschool educational organizations on the basis of pedagogical technologies should be directed at the recipients. Also, in addition to creating conditions for mastering educational material, taking into account their personal and joint activities with the teacher, education and training regularly develop children's activity and curiosity throughout the training, meet the requirements of technology for learning or enables quick involvement in production activities. Otherwise, tasks that are weak, not clear enough, or do not have a clear outcome can lead to an ineffective completion of the training. The advantages of classes organized on the basis of interactive pedagogical technologies are that such a system of classes serves as the basis of science that sharpens thinking, forms boundless love for the Motherland, loyalty, civic ethics and democratic culture. Working with groups, discussion, problem-based teaching, brainstorming methods, as well as working with tables, written works expressing independent opinion, and writing essays in the teaching of subjects increase the activity of students. Such classes conducted on the basis of these methods save time and deliver new knowledge to the student.

therefore, at the same time, problematic situations that make the child think, encourage deep observation, attract all attention,

he will be able to come out of the situation with the right conclusions in debates, and will be able to connect and summarize his acquired knowledge with other topics. The current educational development has brought a new direction - innovative pedagogy to the field. The term "innovative pedagogy" and researches related to it appeared in Western Europe and the USA in the 60s. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American innovator E.

Rogers. He studies the classification of categories (types) of the participants of the innovation process, their attitude to the innovation, their readiness to perceive it. Pedagogical technology - studies the problems of using modern pedagogical technologies in the process of education and training, increasing the effectiveness of the process of education and training based on the technological approach.

Turning to the dictionary meaning of the word technology, this word is derived from Greek and means techno-skill, art, logos - teaching, science. It follows that the word technology is added to other terms and fulfills the tasks of developing this field and improving its skills. In general, technology is an objective process that prepares the stage of educational evolution to solve qualitatively new issues.

New technologies have opened up great educational opportunities. The qualitative changes that are taking place show that the usual explanatory teaching processes have begun to go beyond the limits of the teachers' professional capabilities. The new technical, informational, printed, audio and exhibition tools that have come into existence bring many innovations to the educational process with new methods in their own way and remain an inseparable part of it. However, the uniqueness of the pedagogical technological process, its priority over traditional forms, and methods of real solution to the problems of modern education have not yet been fully studied. Many foreign and Uzbek authors write about it. But everyone believes that pedagogical technologies will have priority in the future. Currently, educational technology is not only an auxiliary tool, but it is understood as a new system that plays a major role in the development of the educational process and changes its organizational forms, methods, and content. This, in turn, affects the pedagogical thinking of the teacher and the student. Such a description of technology shows the importance of the integral connection between all the components of the educational process, the mutual cooperation of the pedagogue and the student. The student turns from a passive object of

education into an active subject of education and training, and as an active subject participates in this process with the teacher, strives to learn independently. Organization of the learning process in innovative ways, i.e., modern pedagogical technologies from the primary education period, is highly effective in the educational system. This means that primary education is the foundation of general secondary education. Building this foundation in a solid way will facilitate the transition of educational processes in the future. It is self-evident that pedagogical technologies established from primary education serve as the first stage in the formation of subsequent periods of education.

CONCLUSION

One of the important conditions for the formation of children's interest in knowledge may be the creation of an emotional situation, the need for knowledge and the development of conscious thinking. Activity is included in the structure of children's cognitive activity, that is, it is such work that intellectual, volitional, emotional processes that enliven cognitive activity are manifested together. For active cognitive activity, comprehensive, deep interest in knowledge, specific effort, attention, and mental and physical forces necessary to achieve the set goal should be focused. Cognitive activity is individual, it is not an innate ability of a person, but his is formed in the process of behavior.

From the youth of children:

- deep, comprehensive interest in knowledge and educational goals;
- active manifestation of mental, physical and intellectual strength;
- gathering attention, memory, will and other mental qualities;
- reproductive activity. Readiness to acquire "ready-made knowledge" and intensive processing activities apply in this;
- applicative activity — it is characterized by readiness for intensive choice-making activity;

- activity in interpretation - willingness to actively interpret, explain and reveal the meaning;
- productive (effective) activity - it is characterized by readiness to intensively create new things. The development of cognitive activity includes several stages:
 - activity in practical activities, manifested in the pursuit of independent behavior;
 - the desire to acquire the essence and principles of the phenomena being studied;
 - creative activity is the highest stage, it consists of causal connection, conviction of the authenticity of creative thought, its vital and cognitive value.

The analysis of the literature on pedagogy and psychology allows us to make the following conclusion: the revitalization of cognitive activity in teaching literally means the activity of thinking. Thinking activity is manifested in cognitive activity in purposeful analysis and synthesis, concretization and systematization of educational materials, application of induction and deduction, acquisition of the knowledge system, development of worldviews and imaginations and concepts. the development of children's creative activity is characterized by the ability of a person to penetrate deeply into the essence of the things and events being studied and to bring elements of innovation and creativity into the cognitive activity. These concepts complement each other. Because a person's activity is manifested in his independent actions, on the contrary, activity often requires independent actions.

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